

Rust Dyeing on Rayon Fabric and its Evaluation

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Abstract:

Background: Textile wet processing not only uses toxic chemicals that are harmful to people and the environment but also uses a large number of non-renewable resources, leading to their depletion. The study on rust dyeing of rayon fabric was conducted, to address these issues by exploring the use of rusted objects to produce unique designs using very low quantities of water and chemicals.

Methods: Rust dyeing was carried out using two methods: Method I used vinegar as a mordant and steaming (for 1 hour) for fixation, and Method II was carried out for 3 days in the absence of vinegar and steaming. Both the samples were visually assessed and tested for their physical properties (tensile strength and bending length), colour fastness, pH, and anti-microbial properties. The samples were also aged and assessed for the above-mentioned properties after aging. This was done mainly to evaluate the change in the tensile strength of the fabric.

Results and Conclusion: The results obtained were good, as both methods showed excellent colour fastness properties. Method II came out to be more economical, sustainable, and safer. Using this approach, the fabric experienced lesser loss of strength but gave a deeper range of shades and sharp imprints.

Keywords: Color fast, Dyeing, Iron, Rayon, Rust, Sustainable

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1. Introduction

The textile and apparel sector is unsavoury these days due to the number of problems it is causing to the environment, as well as the people living in it. To recover its reputation, it needs to restore its structure by slowing down the consumption of water and various chemicals [1]. Now, the industry is working to achieve a balance between the development of the economy and the protection of the environment [2]. Some brands have started using natural dyes considering the ill effects of synthetic dyes on the environment and human health [3]. On the other hand, there are brands developing new and eco-friendly techniques of dyeing and printing, like CO₂-based dyeing (aka, water-less dyeing), invented by a Dutch company named Dyecoo; air dyeing developed by Colorep Inc. [4]; salt-free dyeing by using ECOFAST Pure developed by Dow Company [4,5], dyeing through pigments extracted from microbes and dyeing with REYCROM, powder dyes extracted from textile fibres, developed by Italy-based Officina+39 [6].

Contact dyeing is one of the traditional techniques of dyeing, which also uses very few chemicals and provides beautiful designs by creating bundles with the use of natural materials in low liquor ratios [7]. According to Kadolph and Casselman [8], contact dyeing has the potential to be a more sustainable way of dyeing than immersion dyeing, with the benefits of lower costs, fewer equipment, less labour, safer methods, and reduced water consumption. Kadolph and Casselman [8] highlighted contact dyeing as a cost-effective method for generating intricate patterns and colours using novel materials like organic waste and kitchen pantry items.

Eco-printing is a type of art that uses natural dyes found in plants, fruits, vegetables, waste materials, by-products, etc. to make interesting visual effects. It is a contact method that uses plants as natural templates to make amazing and interesting colours, textures, traces, and marks on the surface of the fabric [9]. Similarly, there's another application that is referred to as 'Rust Dyeing'. This technique also uses a similar approach to produce very unique

designs but with rusted objects instead of any natural material. The resulting colours may be slightly similar, but the resulting effect of the colours varies significantly and is quite interesting. Fabrics that are rust-dyed are safe to wear as they satisfy the requirements of safety for different metals like copper, lead, etc. [10].

The process of rust dyeing is already executed using different natural fabrics like cotton, silk, linen, etc. However, this study of rust dyeing was carried out using rayon fabric (which is a man-made fabric) using the same concept and techniques. Rayon is used as a fashion fabric by various brands to develop numerous categories of garments. So, this study will benefit designers, textile specialists, and fashion and textile students as they can adopt this method to produce innovative and interesting styles of garments that are sustainable and eco-friendly. This was an exploratory study where rusted objects were used as a substitute for dyestuff to create different designs on rayon fabrics. These objects, from their sources, are sent to scrap yards for recycling.

The study focuses on using them before they go to recycling. The procedure of rust dyeing uses very few chemicals, water, and energy resources as compared to conventional dyeing techniques. This in turn also reduces the overall cost as fewer materials and resources are used. The study was carried out with the following objectives:

- To dye rayon fabric by using rusted objects with two methods (with/without the use of vinegar and steaming)
- To test the following properties of the rust-dyed fabric before & after aging the samples: anti-microbial, pH, tensile strength, stiffness, colour fastness
- To rust dye stitched garment/product

2. Materials And Methods

The present study, "Rust Dyeing on Rayon Fabric and its Evaluation" was undertaken to assess the feasibility of the process of rust dyeing, which can be an alternative and a sustainable method to produce unique designs on rayon fabric. The dyeing of the fabric and aging of the dyed fabric were carried out in Dyeing & Printing Lab of the Department of Fabric & Apparel Science, Lady Irwin College. The testing of the fabric samples was carried out in the Instrument Lab, Department of Fabric and Apparel Science, Lady Irwin College.

2.1 Materials Used

2.1.1 Fabrics

The following fabrics were used during the study:

- Rayon fabric: Main fabric, used for rust dyeing
- Wool Fabric: Used for making samples for Perspirometer & Laundrometer to check colour fastness to perspiration & washing

2.1.2 Chemicals & Materials

The following chemicals and materials were used for the study:

- Rusted iron objects: Used as dyestuff, for dyeing, procured from nearby households and scrapyards
- White Vinegar: Used for mordanting
- Sodium Chloride (Common Salt, NaCl): Used to make salt water which helps in fixation of the rust

2.2 Methods Used for Rust Dyeing

Rust dyeing was carried out using two methods:

- Using white vinegar and steaming
- Without using vinegar and steaming

Both methods were conducted to assess which one is more sustainable and feasible.

2.2.1 Method I – Rust Dyeing Using White Vinegar and Steaming

Stage I – Preparation of the Fabric

- a. Scouring: It is one of the pre-treatments given to the fabric to remove all kinds of impurities. This process is most important, as it majorly removes the hydrophobic character of the fabric making it more absorbent. The process of scouring was followed by rinsing of fabric with plain water at room temperature.
- b. Mordanting: After scouring, the fabric was mordanted with white vinegar. The vinegar-water solution, with 2 parts water and 1 part vinegar, was used. The fabric was mordanted in this solution for half an hour. This was done to hasten the process of dying.

Stage II – Contact Dyeing Using Iron Objects

- a. Placing of the Rusted Iron Objects: After half an hour, the mordanted fabric was laid out on a big table. The iron objects sourced from different areas were placed over it after planning out the designs [Figure 1]. One can also place the objects randomly to get abstract designs.

Figure 1: Laying Down Rusted Iron Objects

- b. Bundle Formation: After placing the iron objects, a bundle was formed, according to the design and it was then wrapped in a plastic sheet, which helps to keep the fabric moistened. The bundle formation and plastic wrapping ensures that the objects stay there and don't shift or fall.
- c. Dyeing: Once the bundle was formed, it was placed inside the steamer for 1½ hour. The high temperature of the steamer helps the fabric structure to open up and allows the ferric oxide to go inside and form bonds with the fibre.

Stage III – Fixation & Washing

- a. Salt Treatment: After dyeing, the fabric was put in a salt-water bath for 15 minutes, which helped to fix the colour. This is because salt is an electrolyte, which may aid to accelerate the speed of the ferric ions to move toward the fabric.
- b. Washing: The fabric was soaped, washed under running water at room temperature, and dried under the sun. This helps to remove the leftover rust residue (which is in powdered form) from the dyed fabric.

2.2.2. Method II – Rust Dyeing in Absence of White Vinegar and Steaming

Stage I – Preparation of the Fabric

- a. Scouring: Same as Method I

Stage II – Contact Dyeing Using Iron Objects

- a. Placing of the Iron Objects: Same as Method I
- b. Bundle Formation: Same as Method I
- c. Dyeing: Once the bundle was formed, it was placed inside a big tub with little water inside. This bundle was left for 3 days. The water inside the tub helps the fabric to stay moistened and helps the fabric structure to open up, so that dye can penetrate inside and form bonds with the fabric.

Stage III – Fixation & Washing

- a. Salt Treatment: Same as Method I
- b. Washing: The fabric was soaped and washed under running water at room temperature and dried under the sun. This helped to remove the leftover rust residue (which is in powdered form) from the dyed fabric.

2.2 Assessment of the Dyed Samples

After dyeing by both methods, samples were evaluated before and after aging them. Evaluation, a crucial phase of the study, helped to know more about the strengths and weaknesses of this dyeing technique.

Aging of the samples

Aging is a technique where the textile material is exposed to standard heat and moisture which simulates its natural aging. Since rust was the main dyestuff used in the process, it is considered a significant factor in the degradation of fabrics. Therefore, the fabric was wet-heat aged for 72 hours (3 days) at 80°C in a relative humidity of 65% which is equivalent to approximately 25 years of natural aging [11]. This was done to evaluate the difference between the physical and colour fastness properties of the dyed fabric before and after the process of aging.

Various assessments were conducted according to different standards like: Stiffness was assessed by using Shirley Stiffness Tester, Wash Fastness as per the ISO - III test method, light fastness by using MBTF (Mercury Blended Tungsten Filament) Lamp and Light Fastness Tester (Fadometer) [12], crock/rub fastness by using Crock meter [13], Perspiration fastness by using Perspirometer. Furthermore, pH was assessed using the Standard ISO

3071:2020 or AATCC 81 method, antimicrobial test as per AATCC 147 method and tensile strength using Tensile Strength Tester. Following formula was used to assess the tensile strength:

$$\text{Elongation \%} = \frac{\text{Initial Length} - \text{Final Length}}{\text{Final Length} - \text{Initial Length}} \times 100$$

Key: **BW:** Before Aging without Steaming Sample, **BS:** Before Aging with Steaming Sample, **AW:** After Aging without Steaming Fabric, **AS:** After Aging with Steaming Sample

2.4 Product Development

The final aim of the study was to develop products using the most efficient and sustainable method for rust dyeing.

3. Results and Discussion

The goal of the present study, "Rust Dyeing on Rayon Fabric and its Evaluation," was to determine whether it was possible to put the rusted iron objects into use and dye the rayon fabric with them to create unique and abstract designs. Two methods were used to apply the rust dye to the fabric, the first method was carried out in the presence of vinegar and steaming, and the second one was done in the absence of vinegar and steam. Color fastness properties and physical properties, like tensile strength and stiffness, were assessed. In addition to these, to check whether it was fit for human skin or human use, a pH and anti-microbial test was also conducted.

3.1 Visual Assessment of Rust-Dyed Samples Using Methods I and II

Dyeing was done using two methods. On comparing the samples dyed with both the methods, Figure 2 and 3 revealed that samples dyed with Method II showed a deeper range of shades and a slightly more uniform and clear impression of the objects used for the process.

Figure 2: Rust Dyed Fabric Using Method I

Figure 3: Rust Dyed Fabric Using method II

3.2 Assessment of Colour Fastness Properties

After dyeing and aging, the 4 samples (BW, BS, AW & AS) were then tested for colour fastness against light, washing, rubbing/crocking and perspiration. The following Tables display the ratings of the same.

Table 1: Wash Fastness Rating of Rust Dyed Samples

Colour Fastness	Type of Method	Grey Scales	Before Aging	After Aging
Wash Fastness	With Vinegar and Steaming (BS)	CC	5	5
		SS	5	5
		SW	5	5
	Without Vinegar and Steaming (BW)	CC	5	5
		SS	5	5
		SW	5	5

Table 2: Light Fastness Rating of Rust Dyed Samples

Colour Fastness	Type of Method	Before Aging	After Aging
Light Fastness	With Vinegar and Steaming (BS)	8	8
	Without Vinegar and Steaming (BW)	8	8

Table 3: Crock/Rub Fastness Rating of Rust Dyed Samples

Colour Fastness	Type of Method	Condition W/D	Grey Scales	Before Aging	After Aging
Crock Fastness	With Vinegar and Steaming (BS)	W	CC	5	5
			CS	5	4/5
		D	CC	5	5
			CS	4	4/5
	Without Vinegar and Steaming (BW)	W	CC	4/5	5
			CS	4/5	4/5
		D	CC	5	5
			CS	4	5

Table 4: Perspiration Fastness Rating of Rust Dyed Samples

Colour Fastness	Medium	Type of Method	Grey Scales	Before Aging	After Aging
Perspiration Fastness	Acidic	With Vinegar and Steaming (BS)	CC	5	5
			SW	5	5
			SS	5	5
		Without Vinegar and Steaming (BW)	CC	5	5
			SW	5	5
			SS	5	5
	Basic	With Vinegar and Steaming (BS)	CC	5	5
			SW	5	5
			SS	5	5
		Without Vinegar and Steaming (BW)	CC	5	5
			CC	5	5

Key: CC – Change in Colour; SS – Staining on the Same Fabric; SW – Staining on Wool Fabric; CS – Staining on Cotton Fabric; W – Wet; D – Dry

As shown by the ratings reported in Table 1, 2, 3, and 4, it was evident that the samples dyed with both methods have an excellent wash, light, and perspiration fastness whereas the crock fastness vary from good to excellent. The reason for this could be the strong complex bonding between rust (ferric ions) and cellulose (hydroxyl groups), which causes the colour to be permanent [14].

3.3 Assessment of the Physical Properties of the Dyed Samples

During the pilot study, due to the use of rusted objects for dyeing, various concerns were raised regarding the physical properties of the dyed fabric, like its stiffness and strength. To address them, assessments for stiffness and tensile strength were conducted.

3.3.1 Tensile Strength

The test assessed tensile strength of dyed fabric to determine if it decreased, focusing on load applied to break the fabric. The strength was also checked after aging the sample. The control sample's load at break and % extension, reported in Table 5, was compared to the dyed samples in both warp and weft directions.

Table 5: Load at Break and % Extension of Control Sample in Warp-wise and Weft-wise Direction

Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	% Extension
Warp-wise	24.4	3.2	1.6	40
Weft-wise	21.5	2.8	1.4	35

Further, the Tables 6, 7, 8 and 9 display the average readings for Load, Peak Value, Elongation and % Extension of the samples before and after they're aged. Additionally, it displays the % Decrease in Load of the same samples.

Table 6: Load at Break and % Extension of Samples Dyed Using Steaming & Vinegar (Before Aging) in Warp-wise and Weft-wise Direction

BEFORE AGING				
Sample Dyed using Steaming & Vinegar				
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	%Extension
Warp-wise				
Average	22.8	3.5	1.3	33.3
% Decrease in Load			6.6 %	
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	% Extension
Weft-wise				
Average	19.5	2.5	1.4	35.8
% Decrease in Load			9.5 %	

Table 7: Load at Break and % Extension of Samples Dyed Without Using Steaming & Vinegar (Before Aging) in Warp-wise and Weft-wise Direction

BEFORE AGING				
Sample Dyed without using Steaming & Vinegar				
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	%Extension
Warp-wise				
Average	22.2	3.3	1.2	22.2
% Decrease in Load			9.2 %	
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	% Extension
Weft-wise				
Average	19.3	3.3	1.4	34.2
% Decrease in Load			10.4 %	

Table 8: Load at Break and % Extension of Samples Dyed Using Steaming & Vinegar (After Aging) in Warp-Wise and Weft-Wise Direction

AFTER AGING				
Sample Dyed using Steaming & Vinegar				
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	%Extension
Warp-wise				
Average	21.2	3.8	1.2	30.8
% Decrease in Load			13.0 %	
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	% Extension
Weft-wise				
Average	19.1	3.5	1.3	32.5
% Decrease in Load			11.3 %	

Table 9: Load at Break and % Extension of Samples Dyed Without Using Steaming & Vinegar (After Aging) in Warp-wise and Weft-wise Direction

AFTER AGING				
Sample Dyed without using Steaming & Vinegar				
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	%Extension
Warp-wise				
Average	19.3	3.4	1.1	27.5
% Decrease in Load			20.8 %	
Direction	Load (kg)	Peak Value	Elongation (in)	% Extension
Weft-wise				

Average	15.9	4.3	1.2	29.2
% Decrease in Load			26.0 %	

Tables 6, 7, 8, and 9 reveal that the fabric's strength slightly decreased after dyeing fabric with rusted objects, with Method II showing slightly more loss compared to Method I. This is because, in Method II, the fabric was kept in contact with the rusted articles for 3 days, causing an increase in the concentration of the dye molecules in the fabric affecting its strength. Furthermore, post-aged dyed samples show reduced strength compared to rust-dyed samples that weren't aged, due to less load applied to break the aged fabric.

The % Extension of all the samples was calculated and found to be more in the weft-wise direction, maybe because in a woven structure, weft yarns are more loosely woven than warp yarns.

3.3.2 Bending Length

The bending lengths of control and dyed samples reported in Tables 10 and 11, respectively, reveal that there was no significant difference except in warp direction, which was slightly less than that of the control sample, suggesting the technique didn't significantly affect fabric stiffness when kept for 1½ hours in Method I and 3 days in Method II. This may increase if the time of contact is increased.

Table 10: Bending Length of the Control Sample in Warp-wise & Weft-wise Direction

Control Sample	Sides	Directions	
		Warp-wise	Weft-wise
Readings (cm)	Front	1.5	1.1
	Back	1.5	1.0

Table 11: Bending Length of the Dyed Samples in Warp-wise & Weft-wise Direction

Aging	Before Aging				After Aging			
Method	With Vinegar and Steaming (BS)		Without Vinegar and Steaming (BW)		With Vinegar and Steaming (AS)		With Vinegar and Steaming (AS)	
Direction	W _p	W _f	W _p	W _f	W _p	W _f	W _p	W _f
Average of Readings (cm)	1.13	1.17	1.22	1.08	1.20	1.03	1.23	1.10

3.4 Assessment of the pH Properties of the Dyed Samples

On testing, the results which are presented in Table 12, were found to be in the range of 6.8 – 7.5, which is likely to fall within the neutral range and is an acceptable range of fabric pH for adults. This meant that the garment made from rust-dyed fabric can be comfortably used by human being, as rust didn't change the pH of the fabric.

Table 12: Resulted pH of the Rust Dyed Samples

Aging	Before Aging		After Aging	
Method	With Vinegar and Steaming (BS)	Without Vinegar and Steaming (BW)	With Vinegar and Steaming (AS)	Without Vinegar and Steaming (AW)
Average of Readings	6.8	7.4	7.5	7.3

3.5 Assessment of the Antimicrobial Properties of the Dyed Samples

The study evaluated the anti-microbial activity of control and rust-dyed samples against Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*. The results showed minimal growth of *S. aureus* (Figure 4) and *E. coli* (Figure 5) on the dyed fabrics, implying the possibility of slight antibacterial properties in the dyed fabric.

Figure 4 - Qualitative Evaluation of Anti-Microbial Activity of Control and Rust Dyed Samples in Neutral Medium against Gram Positive Bacteria (*S. aureus*) [(a) Control Rayon Sample, (b) Before Aging with Steaming & Vinegar, (c) Before Aging without Steaming & Vinegar, (d) After Aging with Steaming & Vinegar, (e) After Aging without Steaming & Vinegar]

Figure 5 - Qualitative Evaluation of Anti-Microbial Activity of Control and Rust Dyed Samples in Neutral Medium against Gram Negative Bacteria (*E. coli*) [(a) Control Rayon Sample, (b) Before Aging with Steaming & Vinegar, (c) Before Aging without Steaming & Vinegar, (d) After Aging with Steaming & Vinegar, (e) After Aging without Steaming & Vinegar]

3.6 Product Development

The product was developed using Method II, in which rust dyeing was done in the absence of vinegar and steaming. The reason for this is that this method is much more efficient as it uses less water, energy and chemicals. The products developed were a tank top and a cushion cover as shown in Figure 6 and 7 respectively.

Figure 6: Tank Top Made with Rust Dyeing

Figure 7: Cushion Cover Made with Rust Dyeing

4. Summary and Conclusion

This study used two methods for carrying out rust dyeing. Out of the two methods, Method II, where dyeing took place in the absence of vinegar and steam, showed deeper shades of colour and slightly clearer impressions of the objects used, whereas samples dyed using Method I showed lighter shades of orange and brown. All the samples showed great fastness properties due to the formation of strong complexes between ferric ions and the hydroxyl groups of cellulose present in rayon fabric. Furthermore, the tensile strength decreases as the fabric is aged, and it also depends on the time of contact. It will decrease with an increase in the concentration of dye molecules and time of contact. The rust-dyed fabric proved to be safe and comfortable for human skin, as its pH ranged from 6.8 to 7.5. Additionally, it showed little anti-bacterial properties also. The absence of hazardous chemicals, low water consumption, and energy-intensive procedures led to the further conclusion that Method II is safer and sustainable. This research may have future implications for enhancing fabric strength through rusted object dyeing. Investigating different contact durations can inform improvements in color fastness and physical properties across various fabric types, potentially leading to innovative and sustainable designs.

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